

Women's Voices in Digital Islam: The Contested Reception of Women-Led Islamic Preaching on YouTube in Bangladesh.

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Abstract

This study analyzes 5,249 YouTube comments on women-led Islamic preaching videos in Bangladesh to investigate gendered emotional expression, discursive patterns, and audience engagement within digital religious spaces. It pursues two primary objectives: (1) to examine patterns of audience engagement and emotional responses in the comment sections of women-led Islamic preaching videos on YouTube, and (2) to identify broader trends in public reception, gender visibility, and discourse surrounding women's religious leadership within Bangladesh's digital Islamic sphere. Employing a quantitative sentiment analysis approach, we developed a context-specific codebook informed by classical emotion theory and inductive insights from the dataset. Findings reveal a predominance of negative sentiments, particularly judgmental, angry, and gendered hate speech, largely expressed by male commenters. Although female commenters were fewer in number, they exhibited proportionally higher levels of judgmental, angry, and supportive sentiments. Sentiment distribution varied significantly by comment type, gender visibility, and temporal trends. Statistical analyses, including chi-square tests, Poisson regression, and Negative Binomial regression, indicate that supportive, speculative, and surprising sentiments attracted the highest audience engagement (likes), while angry and judgmental sentiments were less positively received. The study highlights the complex interplay of gender, anonymity, and sentiment in shaping affective discourse around women's religious authority in digital Islamic publics.

Keywords: Digital Islam; Sentiment Analysis; Gender and Emotion; YouTube Comments; Religious Authority

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Dear Mohammad Obaydullah Nikari:

Greetings from Tallahassee, Florida!

Thank you for submitting your abstract for the 12th South Asian Media and Cultural Studies Conference to be held on January 29-30, 2026. We appreciate your time and interest.

This year, we received several great abstract proposals from across the globe in line with the conference theme of "Resilience & Renewal". This shows that our SAMCS community is getting bigger and stronger by the year.

On behalf of our organizing committee, I would like to inform you that your abstract was accepted for presentation at the upcoming conference. Congratulations!

As the next step, please confirm your availability by Monday, November 24, 2025. This year, we will have a hybrid event. The keynote address will be in-person on Thursday, January 29 at FSU. All presentation panels will be held virtually, live via Zoom, with some in-person poster presentations on Friday, January 30. Once we have your confirmation, we will send you more details about your participation at the conference.

We will also invite you to submit a 5-minute pre-recorded video of your presentation before the conference. We will include the video in the program after the conference, and we can also use it as a back-up, if presenters have any technical issues during live sessions.

Please confirm your availability for the conference by Monday, November 24, 2025.

We are excited to have you join us virtually for the conference. Please do not hesitate to reach out, if you have any questions or need further information.

More details will be available on the conference website at: bit.ly/samcs26

Best regards,

The Organizing Committee

12th South Asian Media and Cultural Studies Conference

Website: bit.ly/samcs26